

Using Large Language Models as Fitness Functions in Evolutionary Algorithms for Music Generation

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Abstract

Using evolutionary algorithms for music generation is a well-researched approach. Incorporating language models into that process, however, is new. Recently, creating media from text prompts using machine learning models became a common task. For music, the main research on prompt-based generation addresses direct waveform generation. Works on symbolic music usually use other conditionals. Therefore, our concept of combining evolutionary optimization with the language-music model CLaMP presents the first attempt at prompt-based evolutionary music generation. CLaMP's ability of estimating similarities between prompts and music is used to design a fitness function. We show that problem-specific mutation and recombination is advantageous compared to classic approaches when it comes to fulfilling desired musical properties. The overall quality of the resulting melodies is currently limited. The reasons are specific blind spots of the CLaMP model. Our concept and code, however, can easily be adapted and used with any other pre-trained model.

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Evolutionary algorithms (EAs) have a long history of being applied to the task of music generation (Miranda and Biles, 2007). They were applied in real-time music improvising systems (Biles, 1994), human-computer interaction scenarios (Lewis, 2000), highly creative novelty-seeking art concepts (Diaz-Jerez, 2011), and more (Vico et al., 2021). The main concept is to interpret the creation of an artistic object as an iterative optimization problem. The creation is performed step-wise and seeks for an optimal solution based on a predefined fitness function. Success or failure mainly depends on the definition of this fitness function, but also having effective variation operators to create new solution candidates is crucial.

In the past, many attempts tried to formalize aesthetics, usually based on music theory (Ebcioğlu, 1988; Fernandez and Vico, 2013). Also the complexity of artistic objects (Schmidhuber, 1997), self-similarity (Foote, 1999), and human feedback prediction (Ostermann et al., 2022) were considered as objectives. Recent approaches aim to incorporate deep learning models. However, the idea of using neural networks in fitness functions is not new (Spector and Alpern, 1995; Biles, 1996; Gounaropoulos and Johnson, 2006). The advantage of large models is that they are not highly optimized on single small-scoped tasks, but can be reused as foundation models (Yuan, 2023). That makes it possible to creatively build fitness functions from them as long as the parameters of the pre-trained model are available. The willingness to freely share is a current trend. Therefore, we rather expect this possibility to further expand in the future, which will facilitate the application of approaches like ours and improve results. We also published the code of our generative EA.¹

¹Code: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15880276>

1.2 Image Generation with Language Models

The main inspiration for our work was Tian and Ha (2022). They applied the image-description model CLIP (*Contrastive Language-Image Pre-training* (Radford et al., 2021)) to abstract image generation. With an artistic goal in mind, CLIP is used as fitness function. 2D-images consisting of colored triangles are evolved using Evolutionary Strategies (Eiben and Smith, 2015, Sec.6.2) to fit a given prompt. Edges and color are coded into a genotype representation.

CLIP itself uses *contrastive learning* (details follow in Section 2) to learn relationships between images and text prompts. The EA maximizes the similarity score between them. It was shown by example that the concept works and is capable of producing images matching a given prompt in a way that mental concepts are recognizable.

In the present work, we will analogously use CLaMP (*Contrastive Language-Music Pre-training*, (Wu et al., 2023a)) as a fitness function to generate music from text input. CLaMP learned text-to-music relationships in the same way CLIP did for text-to-image. We will investigate if CLaMP in combination with our EA is able to generate monophonic melodies that match basic musical attributes. The utilization of CLaMP will result in a generative system that receives free text prompts as input and generates music based upon them.

1.3 Melody Generation and Evolutionary Algorithms

The idea of automatic melody generation is ancient. The first music algorithm ever developed by Guido d’Arezzo (ca. 991–1033), an Italian monk and music theorist, addressed the problem by translating song lyrics to pitch sequences. The musical dice games (Mozart, 1862), a popular pastime from the 18th century, let amateurs compose pleasing melodies. And also Arnold Schönberg’s twelve-tone technique (Schönberg, 1950) can be interpreted as a melody algorithm, as it creates monophonic pitch sequences, however, melodic qualities are not usually associated with it.

In the computer age, the idea of feeding music theory knowledge into a rule-based expert system that may then compose music like the great masters aroused fascination (Ebcioğlu, 1988). Later, advanced methods of computational intelligence were applied (Fernandez and Vico, 2013). Creating melodies is still one of the most frequently researched challenges in automatic music generation (Civit et al., 2022). Some early examples achieved human-like qualities using data-based approaches (Cope, 1996). Rule-based systems were successful especially in combination with EAs (Miranda and Biles, 2007). In the context of natural language as an input, however, the vocabulary never grew beyond a few words (Gounaropoulos and Johnson, 2006).

Recently, text-to-art models became very popular (Zhou and Shimada, 2023). Text-to-music still is challenging, but clearly progress is made (Agostinelli et al., 2023; Copet et al., 2024). Rhythm and timbre are highlights of those models. A weak point clearly remains the melodic quality. Conditioning on a given melody is a typical feature. For symbolic music, various conditional models exist, but none of them uses natural language text descriptions. An overview is provided by von Rütte et al. (2023, Sec. 2.1).

To conclude, EAs are common and well-researched in the context of automatic melody generation and music generation in general (Fernandez and Vico, 2013; Vico et al., 2021). What is particularly new to our approach, however, is to be able to use free text prompts as semantic user input to a musical EA.

2 Contrastive Language-Music Pre-training (CLaMP)

Following the idea of CLIP (Radford et al., 2021), CLaMP (Wu et al., 2023a) was designed and built to predict similarities between text and music. The concept of *contrastive learning* aims to compare data from different feature spaces in a single shared feature space. Therefore, CLaMP’s dataset consisted of matching music-text pairs (Wu et al., 2023b). CLaMP has a text encoder f_t and a music encoder f_m . The cosine similarity between two encoded feature vectors is interpreted as a score of text-music matching. The goal of the training process is to maximize the score between both encoder outputs for matching text-music pairs while simultaneously minimizing the similarity for all non-matching pairs. Under those considerations, the formula of the contrastive loss for a batch of N

music-text pairs $(m_i, t_i)_{i=1}^N$ is

$$\mathcal{L}_C = -\frac{1}{2N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\log \frac{\exp(f_m(m_i)f_t(t_i)/\tau)}{\sum_{j=1}^N \mathbb{1}_{i \neq j} \exp(f_m(m_i)f_t(t_j)/\tau)} + \log \frac{\exp(f_m(m_i)f_t(t_i)/\tau)}{\sum_{j=1}^N \mathbb{1}_{i \neq j} \exp(f_m(m_j)f_t(t_i)/\tau)} \right),$$

where τ is the temperature controlling the sharpness of the softmax distribution ($\tau = 0.2$ was used for CLaMP), and $\mathbb{1}_{i \neq j}$ equals 1 if $i \neq j$ else 0. For further details, see Wu et al. (2023a).

The text encoder of CLaMP is pre-trained. It uses DistillRoBERTa (Sanh et al., 2019), a lightweight version of the transformer-based language model RoBERTa (Liu et al., 2019). The music encoder is trained to align to the outputs of DistillRoBERTa for matching pairs. Its architecture was inspired by Masked Autoencoder (He et al., 2021) and it works on music coded in ABC notation. In a pre-processing step, meta information such as title, author or lyrics is removed from the ABC files so that the encoder works exclusively on the musical information. Basic explanation of the ABC notation follows in Section 3.2.2.

Generally, CLaMP is able to perform two types of cross-modal tasks (Wu et al., 2023a, Fig.4):

- (a) **Semantic Search:** Several pieces of music are compared to one single text prompt, so that the piece that is best described by the prompt can be identified.
- (b) **Zero-shot Classification** Several text prompts are compared to one piece of music, so that the prompt that best describes the given piece can be identified.

Type (a) corresponds to the functionality we need for our EA.

3 Evolutionary Algorithm

3.1 General Concept

Evolutionary algorithms are stochastic search methods that algorithmically imitate the concept of biological evolution, which originates from Darwin (1859). It is also a metaheuristic optimization algorithm and, therefore, can be applied similarly to diverse application scenarios with only few modifications. A population of individuals that present potential solutions to a problem are altered over and over again in an evolutionary loop until a stopping criterion is fulfilled. The selection of parents, the reproduction of new individuals by recombination and mutation, and the iterative replacement of the current population with better solutions are the main aspects of an EA (Eiben and Smith, 2015).

In the following subsections, all components of our specifically designed EA are explained. The foundation of every EA is the definition of its search space, which is mainly defined by the representation of the individuals, that, in our case, represent melodies (see Section 3.2). The melody individuals must be compiled from their genotypic form to a phenotype (in our case ABC notation) and have their fitness evaluated in order to introduce evolution pressure towards better melodies. In Section 3.3, we explain how initialization and variation are realized. Technical details of integrating CLaMP as fitness function are presented in Section 3.4.

Figure 1 visualizes our evolutionary loop. It starts with initializing random individuals. Variation is introduced by recombination and mutation. Then they are compiled to phenotypes and evaluated using CLaMP assigning fitness values. CLaMP therefore considers the initially provided text prompt and acts as a music critic (Ostermann et al., 2022) that bases its decision on that prompt. The population is then substituted by individuals with greater fitness. After a fixed number of iterations, the melody individual with the greatest fitness present in the current population is chosen as the final solution.

3.2 Representation of Melody Individuals

Music as an art form is very complex, and perceptions can vary subjectively. Compared to images, music has a temporal component, which makes it more comparable to video. Polyphony, chords, instruments with different timbres, and many more aspects increase the complexity of symbolic music. Therefore, symbolic representations are highly affected by the curse of dimensionality (Ostermann, 2023). Notation of music is also ambiguous when representing acoustic objects. For example, a

Figure 1: General loop of the evolutionary algorithm for generative music

Figure 2: Two octaves of the C major scale with pitch names

quarter note played at 120 BPM has the same acoustic realization as an eighth note played at 60 BPM. The same applies to ABC when considering the so-called *unit length*, which defines the minimal note duration having the effect of quantization. Using different unit lengths, the exact same piece can be notated in multiple ways.

In order to cope with that complexity in our novel approach, we decided to start our study as simplistic as possible. We only considered a small subset of modern Western notation by reducing our representation to monophonic melodies in the key of C major in 4/4 time signature. Further, we only generate melodies with notes from the two octaves between c' and c'' , which can be notated using a treble clef as shown in Figure 2. We omitted accidentals and concentrated on diatonic melodies (i.e. only white keys allowed).

3.2.1 Genotype

For the genotype representation, we focus on the two main attributes of a musical note: pitches and durations. We encode them in two integer sequences of equal length (cf. Figure 3a). We omit the properties of loudness and timbre, which is common in evolutionary melody generation (Miranda and Biles, 2007, cf. Chap. 2.4.1). The loudness is considered to be equal for all notes. The timbre is considered to be less important, since the human perception will interpret the same sequence of notes played by different instruments as being the same melody (Ebeling, 2019).

Figure 3: Schematic representation of a melody

Table 1: Genotype-Phenotype-Pitch-Coding

Genotype code	-1	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
ABC strings	z	C	D	E	F	G	A	B	c	d	e	f	g	a	b	c'
Pitch names	rest	c'	d'	e'	f'	g'	a'	b'	c''	d''	e''	f''	g''	a''	b''	c'''

Table 2: Genotype-Phenotype-Duration-Coding

Coding in genotype	1	2	4
String in ABC notation	<empty string>	2	4
Written note duration			
Written rest duration			

3.2.2 Phenotype

CLaMP uses the ABC notation as its input format. It therefore also builds the foundation for the phenotype, as multiple conversions may result in a loss of information (e.g. genotype \rightarrow MIDI \rightarrow ABC). The ABC syntax is formally defined by Walshaw (2011). ABC is a text-based shorthand notation, which, in contrast to other well-known formats such as MusicXML or MIDI, can be read by humans in a similar way as modern Western music notation.

A music piece in ABC consists of a header and a body. Musical information such as time signature (M:), key signature (K:), and the unit length (L:) are defined inside the header. Meta information such as title, composer or a reference number can also be specified in the header. The body contains the actual music.

As already discussed, we need to restrict the complexity of our melodies. Therefore, we use a fixed ABC header with a fixed time signature and key. Eighth notes are set as the minimal unit length.

The translation of notes from genotype to phenotype is based on two translation tables (see Tables 1 and 2). Each integer value is translated into a corresponding string. While iterating through the two genotype sequences, the measures must be tracked, as bar lines are explicitly written in ABC and considered as tokens by CLaMP. Therefore, notes longer than the remaining duration of the current measure are split in two parts and connected by a *tie* across the bar line. Notes overlapping the middle of a measure are split in the same way. This is a common convention in modern Western notation (Gould, 2011) to make sightreading easier. This may appear to be cosmetic effort only, but in fact it is crucial because CLaMP’s music encoder uses a technique called *bar patching* (Wu et al., 2023a), i.e. ties will make a difference. For the same reason, we fill the last bar with rests (cf. z z2 in Figure 3b) to place a rhythmically correct bar line as the last token of the phenotype. The fully compiled phenotype consists of the fixed ABC header followed by the translated genotype as body (cf. Figure 3b).

3.3 Growing a Melody

The design of an EA does not necessarily have an impact on the quality of final solutions. Therefore, we decided to compare a rather conventional, theory-grounded evolutionary search strategy with a customized approach incorporating domain knowledge (i.e. music theory). In the following, we refer to those two search strategies as **classic** and **growing**, respectively. The latter is inspired by the concept of musical ideas that grow, like Worth and Stepney (2005). The individuals start with a genotype sequence length of 1. The mutation and recombination operators allow for expansion. In contrast, the **classic** approach has a fixed number of notes (cf. Figure 3a). Mutation and recombination will ensure that the genotype sequences remain a constant length. However, the actual length of the melody phenotype, which is the sum of its durations, will vary.

3.3.1 Initialization

The initialization of individuals usually is performed random. For **classic**, we therefore fill the genotype sequences with numbers drawn from a uniform distribution that spans the search space. For **growing**, the individuals are initialized as equal clones containing just one c' as quarter note. The genotype therefore consists of two sequences of length 1 with pitch 0 and duration 2 (cf. Figure 3a). In ABC notation, this is translated to C2 (assuming unit length L: 1/8).

3.3.2 Mutation

For **classic**, the choice of a mutation operator was straightforward: *point mutation* with drawing uniformly at random from the search space (cf. Tables 1 and 2). Each cell of the two genotype sequences of length l is mutated with a probability of $p = \frac{1}{2l}$. However, if no mutation was applied, at least one random cell is chosen. That way, less mutated offsprings are more likely, but multiple mutations are possible.

We anticipated that this arbitrary search might cause problems in our domain, and wanted to test against a domain-specific mutation operator. For **growing**, we therefore decided to restrict mutations by assumptions based on music theory and auditory gestalt theory (Ebeling, 2019; Herborn, 2021).

Considering the pitch sequence, we wanted that big interval leaps should occur less often, which is usually the case for catchy melodies (sometimes assessed by their ability to be sung, which is mainly anti-correlated to big interval leaps (Herborn, 2021)). Therefore, we substituted the uniform random mutation by a gaussian offset around the former pitch. As standard deviation $\sigma = 2$ was chosen, because in our diatonic search space this equals the interval of a minor or major third. If a zero is drawn, we apply rejection sampling and draw again until mutation occurs. The same applies to mutations that would cause a violation of the search space. One exception is the occurrence of a rest. For inserting a note, we clone either the preceding or successive pitch with equal probability. And with a chance of $p = \frac{1}{16}$ we mutate a present note to become a rest.

Considering the duration sequence, which defines the rhythm, we wanted to restrict changes to apply only locally. In the case of uniform point mutation, a change of one duration in the sequence directly affects the starting position of all following note. For example, if a quarter note is mutated to a half note, each successive note is shifted by the duration of one quarter note to the right. Further, mutating notes in the front of the genotype result in a larger overall change of appearance as mutating notes in the back, which is an undesirable property. Therefore, we instead developed a strategy of splitting and merging notes. First, we uniformly choose a random position in the duration sequence. If a half note is in place, we split that note into two quarter notes of the same pitch. This immediately increases the length of the genotype (i.e. it *grows*). If a quarter note is in place, we either do the same and split it into two eighth notes, or we merge them into one half note with its pitch randomly chosen from one of the two merged pitches. However, if an eighth note is in place, we would want to merge with the eighth note that shares the same beat, in order to avoid heavily syncopated melodies (Kennedy et al., 2013, ‘Syncopation’). That means, if an eighth note is on the right side of the beat (i.e. quarter note), it gets merged with the left side and vice versa.

These music theory guided mutation strategies limit the search space to reasonable candidates, i.e. only well-formed melodies are constructed—at least to the likings of the authors. But it must be conceded, that this as well limits the *creative* potential of the whole process. Therefore, the mutation operator must be identified as a crucial component.

3.3.3 Recombination

For **classic**, we chose *one-point crossover*, as it is the most commonly used recombination strategy (cf. Eiben and Smith, 2015, Sec.3.3). It is computationally simple and preserves larger groups of notes from the melodies than *two-point crossover* or *uniform crossover*. Nevertheless, it also provides better exploration than using mutation only by combining solutions from arbitrary locations in the search space. As the genotype length is constant, one-point-crossover is computationally efficient (can be implemented using fixed-length arrays). However, this may limit the flexibility of resulting melodies.

For **growing**, we attempted to consider melodic principles such as repetition and sequencing (Herborn, 2021). We therefore developed a procedure of copying excerpts from one individual over to another. For two parents, we first choose an arbitrary excerpt of 2 to 6 successive notes from the first parent. This excerpt is then copied to a random position in the second parent, that fulfills the condition to preserve the original syncopation. To do so, we make sure that copied excerpts start at quarter note positions (beats) in both the parent and offspring. This helps that the perceived rhythm of the original melody is retained to some extent in the resulting melody (Ebeling, 2019). Besides, we choose parents at random with replacement, which means an excerpt might not only be copied from one parent to another, but also from one position in an individual to another position within that

same individual. A disadvantage is the need for variable-length genotypes, which makes it less computationally efficient. However, that is negligible as we will explain in Section 3.4.

3.3.4 Selection and Replacement

Finally, a concrete reproduction strategy must be defined. Our population size is $\mu = 10$. In each iteration, we create $\lambda = 50$ offsprings. Two parents are randomly selected from the current population with replacement. Recombination occurs with a probability of $p_{rec} = 0.33$. Otherwise, the new offspring will be a deep copy of one parent. Mutation is always applied.

We perform a $(\mu+\lambda)$ -strategy to choose individuals for the next generation. In Section 4, we will compare the greedy method of *best selection* with the stochastic method of *binary tournaments* (Eiben and Smith, 2015, Sec.5.2.4).

We will omit exhaustive hyperparameter optimization of μ , λ , and p_{rec} , as it is assumed to not essentially change our findings and therefore out of the current scope. For the investigation of generative EA concepts, the first step of proving that optimization towards some creative goal is possible and meaningful is far more important than elaborately tuning effectiveness (Vico et al., 2021). Certainly, the chosen parametrization is not extraordinary for the task of EA music generation.

3.4 CLaMP as a Fitness Function

CLaMP itself calculates similarities between a text prompt and a given piece of music. Due to its GPU-based implementation², CLaMP is able to calculate multiple similarities between a single text prompt and multiple pieces of music in parallel. In our use case, we need to calculate the cosine similarities of multiple melody individuals to the one given text prompt in every iteration of our evolutionary loop in order to find the fittest individuals that then form the next generation.

To speed things up, we load the model onto the GPU once at the start of the program. The given text prompt, which will not change during evolution, is processed once by the text encoder and the resulting feature vector serves as comparator for an entire run. We also reduced the number of I/O accesses, since the original implementation needed to load all music pieces from hard disk. Since we must run inference on the CLaMP model various times, passing the ABC phenotypes in-memory significantly speeds up the process. It is also noteworthy that even if our mutation and recombination operators are implemented in pure Python without much effort spend on optimizing those parts of the code, the runtime efficiency of our EA is mainly limited by the inference speed of the music encoder, which requires tens of times the rest of the code.

4 Results

4.1 Objective Prompting

Evaluating generative models is a hard task (Yang and Lerch, 2020). Complex methodologies were proposed, e.g. formalizing creativity (Jordanous, 2012). Objective measures are desired, but generally elaborate user studies are necessary. In our approach, prompting adds just another dimension to the complexity, as the number of possible prompts is nearly endless. As text-prompt-based music EAs are novel and our efforts already involved a first implementation, we have decided to leave heavy prompt variation for future work. Instead, we attempted to construct prompts, that could be evaluated as objectively as possible in order to diagnose deficits of the EA as well as of the CLaMP model and investigate their causes.

We came up with three prompt pairs, that examine guiding capabilities of CLaMP and reveal its inner understanding of musical properties. If one aims to construct a new melody via text prompting, these are properties that a critic model should be able to process (“understand”). The prompt pairs provided in Table 3 investigate higher and lower notes, faster and slower time feels, and wider or closer voice ranges.

Table 3: Full text prompts and their corresponding identifiers

identifier	full text prompt
low	‘A bass melody with many low notes.’
high	‘A soprano melody with many high notes.’
fast	‘A fast melody with many eighth notes.’
slow	‘A slow melody with many half notes.’
repetitive	‘A monotone melody with many tone repetitions .’
wide	‘A wide-range melody with large interval leaps .’

Figure 4: Mean fitness and melody length from all prompts evolving over time

4.2 Fitness Success of Replacement Strategies

Figure 4 shows the achieved fitness in relation to the calculation budget. Only the finally best individual is considered. The budget is the sum of individual fitness evaluations. Stagnation was observed for a budget of 1 000 000 for all hyperparameter settings. With $\lambda = 50$, this equals 20 000 iterations. Counting by budget is necessary, as we perform μ tournaments evaluating only $2\mu = 20$ offsprings and not $\lambda = 50$ offsprings as for best selection. On the same budget, the number of iterations increases to 50 000. All graphs represent the arithmetic mean of 10 statistical repetition, shadows are the signed standard deviations.

classic performed best with best selection, however, **growing** was unable to grow in length over time getting caught in a local optimum early. This combination will therefore be omitted hereinafter. **growing** benefits from binary tournament selection (‘tourn’) and grows in length as expected by allowing elite individuals to stochastically be removed. **classic**, however, achieves smaller fitness.

4.3 Music-specific Mutation and Recombination

The essential question: Is the fitness value correlated to the perceived similarity of prompt and music. As already discussed, semantics are hard to measure. Therefore, we compare the *prompting success* using the specifically designed prompt pairs from Table 3. Figure 5 shows corresponding musical properties that are expected to align to the semantic intention of the prompts.

Testing *low* against *high* should result in lower and higher pitches on average. We observe that actually the opposite happened for **classic**. Statistical testing of the **growing** approach however showed significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) using one-sided Wilcoxon rank-sum test. Therefore, we find that the music-specific search strategy may be beneficial for the goal of fulfilling prompt semantics of desired pitch. However, the average difference of only one pitch (f’ to g’) is unsatisfying.

Testing *fast* against *slow* should increase the use of smaller and larger durations. **classic** with tournament selection did not work. With best selection, the tendency is slightly positive. But again, only **growing** yields a result, that at least achieved statistical significance, i.e. CLaMP probably had a decisive impact on the search, but the impact is again small.

²<https://github.com/microsoft/muzic/tree/main/clamp> (last accessed on July 14, 2025)

Figure 5: Boxplots of means of 10 statistical runs for the three examined musical properties

Figure 6: Musical properties of corresponding prompts evolving over time

Testing *repetitive* against *wide* should show larger interval leaps in the latter. And again, the same findings can be observed. The average interval difference is significant and the largest for **growing**. Since the prompt of *repetitive* explicitly asked for “tone repetitions”, we counted them: **classic** generated tone repetitions in 9.1% of possible cases for both prompts. **growing** managed to reach 0.186% for *wide* and 0.248% for *repetitive*, which matches the prompts’ semantics.

Figure 6 shows the evolutionary progress of the properties. For **growing**, more change happens over time resulting in more distinct characteristics. For **classic**, the values are relatively constant, which suggests, that further iterations would not contradict the findings. This leads to the interim conclusion that for music melodies, problem-specific mutation and recombination operators are beneficial for finding prompt-matching solutions.

4.4 Quality Assessment of Generated Melodies

Finally, we take a look at the actual melodies. Table 4 shows the first few measures of the best melody per prompt for **growing** and **classic**. For the bigger picture, the experimental outcomes are made fully available online³ including also all premature individuals.

On first impression, *low* and *high* cannot be visually identified. We have to trust the statistics (cf. Figure 5). For the other four prompts, the results seem reasonable, at least for **growing**. *Slow* consists of mainly half notes as desired. *Fast* shows more eighth notes. Further it produced a nice repeating sequence in measures 3 and 4 with different target notes (b’ and d”). For **classic**, the difference is harder to recognize. *Fast* starts with a half note and has also some dotted quarter notes tied to an eighth note, which is the same as a half note but is perceived as rhythmically more complex. Further, the excerpt has fewer eighth notes than *slow*. However, the statistics show, that this is an outlier. *Repetitive* also reveals many tone repetitions for **growing**. This is not true for **classic**. *Wide* shows great interval leaps for both strategies.

Overall, the quality of the melodies is limited. The melodies generated by **classic** sound arbitrary, especially their rhythm. Although the melodies generated by **growing** seem a little more pleasing, the melodies of **classic** all achieve higher fitness. The fitness value itself is no indicator of whether a prompt is semantically fulfilled. This is probably because CLaMP was not trained on robustness

³Full experimental data: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15846566>

Table 4: Examples of fittest melodies for all prompts pairs and the best two search strategies.

growing + binary tournaments		classic + best selection
$f = 0.434$	‘A bass melody with many low notes.’ (<i>low</i>)	$f = 0.577$
$f = 0.470$	‘A soprano melody with many high notes.’ (<i>high</i>)	$f = 0.598$
$f = 0.451$	‘A fast melody with many eighth notes.’ (<i>fast</i>)	$f = 0.598$
$f = 0.501$	‘A slow melody with many half notes.’ (<i>slow</i>)	$f = 0.659$
$f = 0.448$	‘A monotone melody with many tone repetitions .’ (<i>repetitive</i>)	$f = 0.642$
$f = 0.488$	‘A wide-range melody with large interval leaps .’ (<i>wide</i>)	$f = 0.656$

against unrealistic examples. Our approach, however, can be interpreted as an adversarial attack (Szegedy et al., 2014), since we do not use CLaMP with real-world examples as intended, but maximize the input characteristics and thereby risk finding model blind spots. The **classic** version of our EA generously allows for such borderline examples. Nevertheless, the fitness never approximates 1. This can be an indication that CLaMP has at least a vague “understanding” for bizarre candidates. Applying strategies against adversarial attacks to the training procedure of CLaMP could make its predictions more robust, and thus improve our generative concept.

Further, because EA optimization is an iterative process, we are facing intermediate solutions, which to handle is the essential mechanism of diffusion models (Sohl-Dickstein et al., 2015). Those are today state-of-the-art in text-to-image generation, and could be incorporated in our concept as future improvement.

4.5 Discussion and Additional Remarks

The main weak point of our study is to not have extensively investigated prompt variation. Therefore, we spot checked if slight changes have an impact. We tried compressing the sentences to the adjectives only. This did not change the results much. We also tested elongating the prompts, which seemed to make property matching worse. We therefore think, short and precise prompts are easier for the model to process, but further investigation of that, possibly involving automatic prompt optimization (Ramnath et al., 2025), is a promising future direction.

Another attempt was to include all 12 notes from the chromatic scale in the search space. This, however, resulted in grotesque melodies. The model was not at all able to handle this complexity, e.g. not even roughly keeping the specified key. Future work must improve on CLaMP itself. More EA tuning alone will certainly not help.

5 Conclusions and Future Work

In this work, we have transferred the concept of using an image-description model to guide evolutionary art generation to the music domain. We have formalized a procedure of evolving melody individuals and evaluating their similarity to a text prompt using the pre-trained model CLaMP (Wu et al., 2023a). The similarity can then be interpreted as fitness. We have shown that the development of problem-specific mutation and recombination operators is advantageous over classical

approaches and that the combination with stochastic replacement prevents getting caught in local optima. However, the overall quality of the generated music is limited and has a lot of potential for improvement.

The search space of music is incredible large. Therefore, the present work is only an initial step in applying EA optimization to text-to-music prompting. Further, the aspects of training such a complex model acting as a fitness function, ways of evaluating hyperparameter choices (esp. the huge amount of possible prompts), and the qualitative evaluation of art make such a study very expensive.

One of the greatest challenges was to cope with the blind spots of CLaMP. We begun with complex prompts and complex music representations. Soon, we had to limit the scope and do our analysis step by step as presented in Section 4. Very recently, CLaMP has been released in version 2 (Wu et al., 2025) and its integration is clearly the next logical step. However, since models like CLaMP are not initially designed to iteratively evaluate musical objects, but only to handle real-world examples, the choice of the search space will always be highly important. In the future, models could be more specifically designed to cope with unfinished examples, e.g. by incorporating augmentation techniques against adversarial attacks (Szegedy et al., 2014) into the training process or adapting mechanisms from diffusion models (Sohl-Dickstein et al., 2015). However, the presented concept proved to be a fine tool for analyzing robustness and identifying weak points. It also can give interpretable insights about what black-box models have actually learned.

Further we have seen, if there is an immutable (i.e. pre-trained) but large language model available, that shaping the search space through problem-specific mutation and recombination operators is possible and improves the resulting solutions. We were able to show that including knowledge of music theory can yield better results if the fitness model itself falls short in extreme cases. Therefore, it could be even more beneficial to make those operators more rule-based, e.g. by not repeating notes but interpolating them, inserting more planned repetitions, or recombining rhythm and pitches from different parents. Also, a multi-objective fitness function could be introduced, with multiple pre-trained models or a mix of trained models with constraints and rules motivated by music theory, as proposed by (Jaques et al., 2016) in the context of reinforcement learning (RL). Latter discipline, however, could also benefit from our findings. Since we were able to show that growing music is better than using genotypes of constant length, this could be applied vice versa to RL by incorporating curriculum learning (Wang et al., 2022) into generative models. A third approach to improve our EA could be to learn the mutation operator itself from example data.

Lastly, we clearly have to repeat the presented experiments with variations of our prompts. We should also overcome objective prompting at some point and conduct human listening studies, e.g. with prompts including emotions, genre, and similar. But therefore, we first need to improve the overall quality of the generated melodies to not suffer from computer art rejection bias (Horton Jr et al., 2023). A promising solution to that would be to de-automate and involve human artists in the loop, as interactive EAs are also a common and well-researched concept (Biles, 1994).

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